

Moderating Effect Of Audit Committee Independence On Board Characteristics and Audit Quality Of Listed Commercial Banks in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines the moderating effect of audit committee independence on the relationship between board attributes and audit quality among Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX). Specifically, it investigates the effects of board characteristics—such as board size, board independence, and board financial expertise on the quality of audits conducted for these banks. Using a purposive sampling technique, the study analyzes data from 15 DMBs, covering the period from 2014 to 2023. Logistic regression is employed to estimate the probability of high audit quality based on the selected governance attributes. In contrast, board independence was found to have an insignificant impact on audit quality. Furthermore, board size was positively associated with improved audit quality. Additionally, the study finds that the audit committee's independence serves as significant moderators, strengthening the relationship between board financial expertise and audit quality. The study concludes by recommending that the FRCN should prioritize the independence of audit committees by enforcing strict criteria on membership. Audit committees should be composed solely of independent non-executive directors with no financial interests in the company, thereby reinforcing the objectivity of the auditing process. FRCN can work with firms to ensure audit committees are adequately empowered to oversee external auditors and ensure the accuracy and integrity of financial reporting.

Keywords: Audit quality, Board size, Board independence, Board financial expertise, Audit committee independence,

Introduction

Audit quality is widely regarded as the cornerstone of financial reporting integrity and investor confidence. It plays a crucial role in ensuring that financial statements accurately reflect a

company's performance and financial position, fostering transparency and trust in the capital markets. The significance of high-quality audits cannot be overstated, as they serve as a key mechanism for safeguarding the interests of investors, stakeholders, and the broader economy. The reliability of financial statements hinges on the robustness of the audit process, which is designed to detect and prevent errors, fraud, and misreporting (Dauda, Ojo, Oyedokun, & Ajayi-Owoeye, 2018; Mautz & Sharaf, 2022).

Despite increased regulatory oversight, such as the Companies and Allied Matters Act (CAMA) in Nigeria and similar frameworks in other jurisdictions, audit failures remain a persistent problem. These failures have been associated with some of the most high-profile corporate scandals, including those involving Nigerian banks such as Oceanic Bank, Intercontinental Bank, and Heritage Bank, as well as international cases like the collapse of Carillion and Wirecard. These events have sparked intense debates among regulators, practitioners, and researchers, all seeking effective solutions to address the unprecedented corporate failures. A central theme that resonates throughout these scandals is the lack of a robust corporate governance structure capable of curbing managerial excesses and ensuring accountability (Gendron, 2020). This underscores the need for more stringent governance frameworks and independent oversight mechanisms, such as effective audit committees, to restore trust and confidence in financial markets.

The Board of Directors plays a pivotal role in corporate governance by overseeing the management of the company and ensuring that the organization's operations align with the interests of its shareholders and stakeholders. The board is responsible for setting the strategic direction of the firm, approving major financial decisions, and establishing policies that guide its operations. One of its key functions is to ensure that there is adequate oversight of financial reporting and internal controls, often through the establishment of subcommittees such as the Audit Committee (Tricker, 2019).

Recent research suggests that board characteristics, such as independence, financial expertise, diversity, and size, are significant determinants of audit quality (Alfraih, 2022; Hasan et al., 2021). Board independence enhances monitoring effectiveness by reducing management's influence over financial reporting, thereby improving audit quality (Zgarni, Halioui & Zehri, 2021). Financial expertise among board members ensures a better understanding of complex accounting and auditing matters, strengthening oversight of external auditors (Al-Dhamari & Chandren, 2023). Board diversity, particularly gender diversity, has been linked to more rigorous corporate governance practices, which improve financial reporting quality and reduce earnings management (Mohd-Saleh et al., 2022). Additionally, board size plays a critical role, as a well-structured board with adequate size enhances decision-making and audit effectiveness, though excessively large boards may encounter coordination challenges (Adegbite, Amaeshi & Amao, 2022).

In addition to board characteristics, audit committee independence plays a crucial moderating role in enhancing audit quality (Al-Dhamari & Chandren, 2023; Zgarni, Halioui & Zehri, 2021). An independent audit committee strengthens the board's oversight function by ensuring that external auditors remain objective and free from managerial influence (Hasan et al., 2021). Studies suggest that when an audit committee is independent, it enhances the effectiveness of board characteristics such as financial expertise, diversity, and size—in improving audit quality (Ojo, Oyedokun, & Fodio, 2020; Mohd-Saleh et al., 2022). For instance, an independent audit committee can mitigate

the risk of earnings management and ensure a higher level of financial reporting transparency (Adegbite, Amaeshi & Amao, 2022).

In the context of Nigerian commercial banks, regulatory frameworks such as the Companies and Allied Matters Act (CAMA) and the National Code of Corporate Governance (NCCG) emphasize the importance of audit committee independence in strengthening financial oversight. Given the history of corporate scandals in the Nigerian banking sector, ensuring that audit committees operate independently is critical to fostering investor confidence and financial stability (Okike, 2023; Oyedokun, Tade, Eso, & Abiodun-Afolabi, 2024).

Although a considerable amount of literature exists on the interaction between corporate governance mechanisms and audit quality (Linh & Thuy, 2024; Kalia et al., 2023; Alexeyeva et al., 2023; Nguyen & Nguyen, 2024), a critical knowledge gap remains regarding the moderating role of audit committee independence in this relationship. Most existing studies primarily focus on board characteristics such as board independence, financial expertise, and diversity, with limited attention given to how an independent audit committee enhances audit quality

Furthermore, a sectoral gap exists, as much of the literature centers on non-financial sectors, such as manufacturing, technology, and services, while research on the banking industry remains scarce despite its systemic importance. It is against the backdrop that this study examined the moderating effect of audit committee independence on board characteristics and audit quality of listed commercial banks in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Audit Quality

Audit quality is a fundamental pillar of financial reporting integrity, ensuring that financial statements accurately represent a firm's financial position and performance. High-quality audits enhance investor confidence, facilitate capital market efficiency, and reduce information asymmetry between management and stakeholders (DeFond & Zhang, 2022; Oyedokun, Idowu, Abiodun-Afolabi, & Eso, 2024). The International Auditing and Assurance Standards Board (IAASB, 2021) defines audit quality as the ability of auditors to issue accurate and independent audit opinions based on professional skepticism, adherence to auditing standards, and sufficient audit evidence.

In the Nigerian context, regulatory frameworks such as the Companies and Allied Matters Act (CAMA) 2020, the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) Code of Corporate Governance, and the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Prudential Guidelines emphasize the role of external audits in maintaining financial transparency. However, persistent issues such as auditor-client relationships, audit committee inefficiencies, and management influence over audit outcomes pose challenges to audit quality in Nigerian banks (Adegbite et al., 2023).

Board Independence

Board independence refers to the extent to which a company's board of directors consists of non-executive, independent members who are free from managerial influence and can effectively oversee corporate governance and financial reporting processes (Linh & Thuy, 2024; Alexeyeva

et al., 2023). An independent board plays a critical role in ensuring audit quality, mitigating earnings management, and enhancing shareholder protection (Kalia et al., 2023).

Board independence is a key determinant of corporate governance and plays a pivotal role in ensuring the quality of audits and the integrity of financial reporting. In the context of corporate governance, board independence refers to the proportion of non-executive directors who have no material or familial relationship with the company's management, allowing them to make objective decisions that align with shareholders' interests (Kalia et al., 2023). The principle of board independence aims to reduce potential conflicts of interest, ensuring that directors can provide unbiased oversight over management's actions, including the audit process (Linh & Thuy, 2024).

The relationship between board independence and audit quality is grounded in the agency theory, which emphasizes that independent directors help align the interests of management and shareholders, mitigating managerial opportunism (DeFond & Zhang, 2022). According to agency theory, the separation of ownership and control in firms leads to potential conflicts, and independent boards serve as a critical mechanism to reduce information asymmetry and ensure that financial statements accurately reflect the company's performance (Gendron, 2020).

Independent directors have been found to improve audit quality through enhanced monitoring and oversight of the audit process (Nguyen & Nguyen, 2024). By ensuring that financial reporting and auditing processes are properly scrutinized, independent boards reduce the likelihood of financial misreporting and fraud. They are less likely to succumb to pressures from management, ensuring that the external auditors' work remains impartial and objective. A higher proportion of independent directors on the board typically results in more rigorous oversight of the audit committee, which plays a direct role in overseeing the audit process and the relationship with external auditors (Alexeyeva et al., 2023; Idowu, Abiodun-Afolabi, Eso, & Oyedokun, 2024).

The role of independent directors in protecting the independence of external auditors is crucial. In firms with independent boards, there is a lower risk of managerial interference with the audit process (DeFond & Zhang, 2022). Independent directors are more likely to ensure that the external auditor has the necessary autonomy to conduct an objective audit, reducing potential conflicts of interest that may arise if auditors have close ties with the management. This autonomy is critical in ensuring that audit reports are not influenced by external pressures, which would otherwise compromise audit quality.

The presence of independent directors can significantly improve financial transparency by ensuring that the company's financial statements are presented accurately, which in turn enhances audit quality. Independent boards are more likely to prioritize the interests of shareholders and other stakeholders by advocating for transparent financial reporting, reducing the opportunity for fraudulent reporting (Alexeyeva et al., 2023). This has a direct impact on the external audit process, as the auditors can rely on the company's financial statements as accurate representations of the company's financial health.

While board independence is critical in improving audit quality, challenges arise in emerging markets, including Nigeria. In the context of Nigerian commercial banks, the effectiveness of independent boards in enhancing audit quality is often hampered by factors such as political interference, lack of financial expertise among independent directors, and weak enforcement of

corporate governance regulations (Hasan et al., 2021). Many independent directors in Nigerian firms are appointed based on political or social connections rather than professional qualifications, leading to a lack of proper oversight and weakened audit quality. Furthermore, regulatory frameworks, although present, are sometimes not effectively enforced, limiting the ability of independent boards to ensure high audit standards (Okike, 2023).

Board Financial Expertise

Board financial expertise refers to the presence of individuals on a company's board of directors who possess the knowledge and skills to understand and evaluate the financial and accounting aspects of the company's operations. This expertise is critical in ensuring that the board is capable of providing effective oversight, particularly when it comes to financial reporting and audit processes. Board members with financial expertise are typically able to scrutinize financial statements, assess audit reports, and engage in meaningful discussions with external auditors, which ultimately contributes to improved audit quality.

Financial expertise is an essential component of effective corporate governance. A board with financial expertise is more likely to make informed decisions about financial reporting and ensure that the company complies with accounting standards and regulations (Gendron, 2020). This expertise allows the board to challenge management on issues related to financial transparency and integrity. In particular, board members with financial backgrounds are better equipped to detect any irregularities in financial statements, thus reducing the risk of financial misreporting and fraud (Linh & Thuy, 2024). Their ability to understand complex financial information contributes to the overall strength of corporate governance and improves the quality of audits by ensuring that the financial information presented to external auditors is accurate and reliable.

The presence of financially knowledgeable board members enhances audit quality by enabling the board to effectively oversee the work of the external auditors. A board with financial expertise can actively engage in discussions with auditors, provide valuable insights into financial issues, and hold both management and auditors accountable for the quality of financial reporting (DeFond & Zhang, 2022). Financially literate directors are more likely to detect discrepancies and biases in financial statements, which ensures that auditors are not compromised by inaccurate or misleading information. Moreover, the expertise allows board members to assess the audit firm's capabilities, contributing to the selection of high-quality auditors who are independent and competent (Nguyen & Nguyen, 2024; Kolade, Abiodun-Afolabi, Abey, & Oyedokun, 2024).

Board financial expertise is directly linked to the improvement of financial reporting quality and transparency. In firms where the board possesses strong financial knowledge, the company is more likely to adhere to financial reporting standards and regulatory requirements. This results in more transparent and accurate financial disclosures, which improves the quality of external audits. Transparent financial statements reduce the risk of manipulation and provide auditors with a clear and reliable basis for their assessments (Alexeyeva et al., 2023). Furthermore, financial expertise on the board fosters a culture of accountability, where the board ensures that all financial information disclosed to shareholders, investors, and regulators is honest and accurate.

The audit committee, a subcommittee of the board, is responsible for overseeing the financial reporting process, including the relationship with external auditors. Financially knowledgeable board members on the audit committee are better able to evaluate the quality of the audits and

ensure that the external auditor's opinion is not unduly influenced by management. The audit committee with strong financial expertise can identify any potential weaknesses in the internal controls, risk management systems, or accounting practices that might affect the quality of financial reporting (Linh & Thuy, 2024). Studies have shown that audit committees with financial expertise are more likely to oversee the audit process effectively, thereby improving audit quality and reducing the likelihood of audit failures (DeFond & Zhang, 2022).

Linh and Thuy (2024) found that firms with financially knowledgeable directors are more likely to exhibit high-quality audits due to the enhanced oversight they provide over the financial reporting and audit processes. Similarly, Kalia et al. (2023) demonstrated that boards with members possessing financial expertise significantly improve the effectiveness of audits by ensuring that the financial statements are accurate and that the auditors maintain independence. Furthermore, studies on Nigerian banks, such as the one by Okike (2023), emphasize the importance of financial expertise on the board in mitigating the risk of financial scandals, as seen in high-profile cases involving banks like Oceanic Bank, Intercontinental Bank, and Heritage Bank.

Board Size

Board size refers to the total number of members serving on a company's board of directors. The size of a board plays a crucial role in the functioning of corporate governance, affecting various aspects such as decision-making, oversight, and the overall quality of financial reporting and audits. The impact of board size on audit quality has been a subject of considerable academic research, with studies suggesting both positive and negative effects depending on the context and specific characteristics of the board.

The size of a board can have a significant impact on corporate governance effectiveness. A larger board may offer a broader diversity of skills, perspectives, and expertise, which could enhance decision-making and provide a more comprehensive oversight of management. On the other hand, a smaller board can facilitate quicker decision-making and potentially be more cohesive in its oversight role (Yermack, 2020). The optimal board size is typically considered a balance between these two extremes. Large boards may suffer from coordination problems, inefficiencies, and a lack of effective communication, which could hinder their ability to monitor management and oversee audit processes effectively (Jensen, 2021).

The relationship between board size and audit quality is complex, as it depends on various factors, including the composition of the board, its diversity, and the presence of independent directors. Research has indicated that board size can influence the quality of audits in different ways. For instance, large boards may be able to bring in diverse expertise and better resources, which can enhance the ability of the board to scrutinize financial reports and ensure high-quality audits (Alexeyeva et al., 2023). However, too large a board can lead to inefficiency and reduced accountability, which might detract from the board's ability to effectively oversee audit processes (Kalia et al., 2023).

On the other hand, smaller boards might have fewer resources and limited perspectives, which could negatively affect the board's ability to ensure the accuracy of financial reporting and audit quality. The monitoring role of the board, which is crucial in maintaining high audit quality, might be less effective with a small, homogeneous group of individuals (Linh & Thuy, 2024). Therefore,

the effect of board size on audit quality can vary depending on the effectiveness of the board members' engagement in the audit process and their ability to collaborate and communicate.

Audit Committee Independence

Audit committee independence refers to the degree to which the members of an organization's audit committee are free from influences that could impair their ability to objectively and effectively oversee the financial reporting process and the audit. The audit committee is a key component of a firm's governance structure, entrusted with overseeing the internal control systems, financial reporting processes, and interactions with external auditors. Its role is especially critical in ensuring the integrity of financial statements and the quality of the audit.

The independence of the audit committee is widely recognized as essential to ensuring unbiased oversight of financial reporting and auditing processes. Independent audit committees are less likely to be influenced by management pressures, conflicts of interest, or other forms of bias that could compromise the accuracy and transparency of financial reports. According to the Institute of Internal Auditors (IIA, 2022), a fully independent audit committee can provide robust oversight, leading to more accurate financial reporting and higher-quality audits, which in turn enhance investor confidence and the firm's overall reputation.

Audit committee independence is typically defined by the absence of relationships or financial interests that could impair objectivity. According to the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC, 2020), the independence of audit committee members is characterized by their lack of ties to the company's management, shareholders, or other related parties. Additionally, independence is often linked to the presence of non-executive or independent directors on the audit committee, particularly those with financial expertise. The SEC and OECD Guidelines on Corporate Governance (2021) require that the audit committee of listed firms must consist solely of independent directors, a provision aimed at strengthening the committee's ability to function autonomously.

The audit committee plays a pivotal role in enhancing audit quality by reviewing the company's internal control systems, approving the scope and approach of the external audit, and ensuring that the audit process is free from management interference. A key responsibility of the audit committee is to select and evaluate external auditors, ensuring that these auditors are truly independent and have the necessary expertise to conduct an objective audit.

Audit committee independence is directly linked to the committee's ability to ensure that auditors perform their duties in an unbiased and thorough manner. For example, in the case of Heritage Bank (2021), the audit committee's independence was essential in detecting potential irregularities in financial reporting, which were identified by an external auditor who operated without management interference. Without such independence, auditors may feel pressured to overlook discrepancies or issues that could damage the company's image, leading to a reduction in audit quality.

Kalia et al. (2023) found that in Nigerian commercial banks, the independence of the audit committee was significantly correlated with higher audit quality. Independent audit committees in these institutions were able to effectively oversee the financial reporting process and ensure that external auditors conducted their work without interference from management.

In contrast, Alexeyeva et al. (2023) observed that in firms with audit committees composed mainly of executives or insiders, audit quality tended to be lower. This is because such audit committees may lack the objectivity needed to challenge management's financial practices, resulting in less rigorous audits. Similarly, Tsalavoutas & Vourvachis (2021) highlighted that audit committees that are not independent may fail to detect fraudulent financial reporting or other issues that an independent committee might identify, thus diminishing audit quality.

Empirical Studies

Almaqtari et al. (2024) examined how changes in board independence moderate the relationship between board characteristics and audit quality. Their study, conducted on firms in emerging markets, found that increased board independence enhances audit quality by improving oversight and reducing managerial influence on external auditors. This finding aligns with Linh and Thuy (2024), who investigated the effect of board expertise, size, and diversity on audit quality in Vietnam. They concluded that firms with larger, more diverse boards and a higher proportion of financial experts tend to have better audit outcomes.

Similarly, Tiwari and Maji (2024) analyzed the impact of corporate governance attributes on audit quality in India. Their study revealed that board independence, alongside board financial expertise, significantly improves audit quality by reducing the likelihood of financial misstatements and audit failures. These findings support the notion that strong board structures play a crucial role in ensuring the credibility of financial reports.

Adebiyi et al. (2024) investigated the moderating effect of audit committee independence on audit firm attributes and audit quality in quoted insurance companies in Nigeria. Their findings indicated that an independent audit committee strengthens the effectiveness of audit firms in detecting and preventing financial misreporting. The study emphasized that audit committee independence is critical in mitigating audit failures, particularly in regulated sectors such as insurance and banking.

In a related study, Alawaqleh et al. (2021) examined the influence of board composition and CEO characteristics on audit quality in Jordanian manufacturing firms. They found that firms with independent audit committees and boards were more likely to engage high-quality audit firms and exhibit greater financial transparency. These findings are consistent with the argument that independent audit committees enhance the objectivity and reliability of the auditing process.

Most empirical studies have focused on general corporate governance mechanisms without considering sectoral differences. While studies such as Almaqtari et al. (2024) and Tiwari and Maji (2024) provide insights into governance structures in emerging economies, there is limited research specifically examining industry-specific factors. For instance, financial institutions such as banks and insurance companies operate in a highly regulated environment, which may influence the effectiveness of governance mechanisms differently compared to manufacturing or service industries.

Despite the extensive research on corporate governance and audit quality, several gaps remain in the literature. First, while studies such as Linh and Thuy (2024) and Tiwari and Maji (2024) have examined board characteristics, they often overlook the interaction between different governance attributes. For example, how board independence interacts with financial expertise and gender diversity in influencing audit quality is still underexplored.

Adebiyi et al. (2024) highlighted the importance of audit committee independence in Nigeria's insurance sector, but similar studies in other industries are scarce. Future research should assess whether audit committee independence has the same impact on audit quality in manufacturing, energy, and telecommunications sectors.

Theoretical Framework

Agency Theory

Agency theory, proposed by Jensen and Meckling (1976), is one of the most widely used frameworks in corporate governance research. It explains the relationship between principals (shareholders) and agents (management), emphasizing the inherent conflict of interest that arises when managers prioritize their own interests over those of shareholders.

In the context of audit quality, agency theory suggests that independent boards and audit committees serve as monitoring mechanisms to reduce opportunistic behaviors by management. When the audit committee is independent, it is more likely to ensure that external auditors perform their duties without bias, thereby improving audit quality (Linh & Thuy, 2024).

Resource Dependence Theory

Resource Dependence Theory (Pfeffer & Salancik, 1978) emphasizes that organizations rely on external resources to function effectively. The theory suggests that having a diverse and financially knowledgeable board and audit committee can provide firms with critical resources that enhance audit quality.

From this perspective, board financial expertise and audit committee independence are essential because they bring in-depth knowledge and professional experience that strengthen financial oversight. A board with financial experts can better assess the quality of external audits and challenge questionable financial practices (Kalia et al., 2023). Additionally, independent audit committees can facilitate the selection of high-quality external auditors, reducing the likelihood of audit failures (Alexeyeva et al., 2023).

Institutional Theory

Institutional theory (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983) explains how regulatory, normative, and cognitive factors influence corporate governance practices. It suggests that firms adopt best governance practices, such as audit committee independence, in response to regulatory pressures and industry norms.

This theory is particularly relevant in emerging economies, where corporate governance structures are still evolving. Nigerian firms have increasingly adopted governance best practices due to pressure from investors, international regulators, and industry competition (Adegbite et al., 2023). However, challenges remain in ensuring full compliance, as some firms may adopt governance reforms only for legitimacy without fully implementing them in practice (Gendron, 2020).

Methodology

Research Design

This study employs an ex post facto research design. The ex post facto design allows for the analysis of historical data without manipulating variables, making it suitable for studies that rely on secondary data sources such as audited financial reports and corporate governance disclosures. This design is widely used in accounting and finance research to assess the impact of governance attributes on financial outcomes.

Population, Sample, and Sampling Techniques

The population of the study comprise 15 DMBs listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as of 31st December 2023.

Table 1 Population of the study

S/N	
1	ACCESS BANK PLC
2	FIDELITY BANK PLC
3	FIRST CITY MONUMENT BANK PLC
4	FIRST BANK NIGERIA
5	GUARANTY TRUST BANK PLC
6	UNION BANK OF NIGERIA PLC
7	UNITED BANK OF AFRICA PLC
8	ZENITH BANK PLC
9	POLARIS BANK PLC
10	STANBIC IBTC BANK PLC
11	STERLING BANK PLC
12	Eco banks
13	UNITY BANK PLC
14	WEMA BANK PLC
15	Jaiz

Source: Researcher's computation 2025

The study employs a censored sampling technique, which considers all 15 DMBs from 2014 to 2023.

Methods of Data Collection

This study employed secondary data collection, sourcing relevant information from the annual reports and financial statements of the selected Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) listed on the

Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX). These reports serve as reliable sources of financial and governance disclosures, providing verifiable data on board characteristics and audit quality.

Technique of Data Analysis and Model Specification

This study adopted logistic regression as the technique of data analysis. The technique allows for estimating the probability of high audit quality based on corporate governance attributes such as board independence, board financial expertise, board size, and audit committee independence.

Model Specification

$$\left(\frac{P(AQ_{it})}{1 - P(AQ_{it})} \right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BI_{it} + \beta_2 BFE_{it} + \beta_3 BS_{it} + \beta_4 ACI_{it} + \beta_5 FS_{it} + \beta_6 (BI_{it} \times ACI_{it}) + \beta_7 (BFE_{it} \times ACI_{it}) + \beta_8 (BS_{it} \times ACI_{it}) +$$

Where:

AQ = Audit Quality

BI = Board Independence

BFE = Board Financial Expertise

BS = Board Size

ACI = Audit Committee Independence

FS = Firm Size for bank iii at time ttt

β_0 = Intercept

β_1 – β_5 = Coefficients measuring the direct effect of each independent variable on audit quality

BI×ACI: This interaction term captures how the effect of Board Independence on audit quality is influenced by the Audit Committee Independence.

BFE×ACI: This term reflects the interaction between Board Financial Expertise and Audit Committee Independence, showing how the presence of an independent audit committee moderates the effect of financial expertise on audit quality.

BS×ACI: This term captures the interaction between Board Size and Audit Committee Independence, revealing how board size's effect on audit quality is affected by the presence of an independent audit committee.

Variable Measurements

Variable	Measurement
Dependent Variable	
Audit Quality (AQ)	Binary variable: 1 = Audit conducted by a Big 4 firm (Deloitte, PwC, EY, KPMG), 0 = Audit conducted by a non-Big 4 firm.
Independent Variables	

Board Independence (BI)	Number of Independent Directors / Total Number of Directors × 100
Board Financial Expertise (BFE)	Number of Directors with Financial Expertise / Total Number of Directors × 100
Board Size (BS)	Total number of directors.
Firm Size (FS)	log(Total Assets)
Moderating Variable	
Audit Committee Independence (ACI)	Number of Independent Members / Total Number of Audit Committee Members × 100

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max
aq	135	.6518519	.4781575	0	1
bs	135	10.06667	1.593831	6	13
bi	135	.152157	.0750198	.0625	.5
bfe	135	.5365121	.1322536	.1666667	.8844
bs_aci	135	2.440487	1.087542	.7692308	5.777778
bi_aci	135	.036854	.0238902	.0083333	.1363636
bfe_aci	135	.1313316	.0696604	.0333333	.35376
fsize	135	7.186333	.9135457	5.529801	10.16481

The descriptive statistics provide insightful details on the key variables in the study. For Audit Quality (AQ), the mean value of 0.6519 indicates that approximately 65% of the banks in the sample are audited by Big 4 firms, with a high standard deviation of 0.4782, suggesting variability in audit quality across the banks. The minimum and maximum values of 0 and 1, respectively, confirm the binary nature of the variable, representing either a Big 4 audit or a non-Big 4 audit.

The Board Size (BS) has a mean of 10.0667, indicating that, on average, the banks in the study have moderately sized boards. The standard deviation of 1.5938 reveals variability in board size, with some banks having as few as 6 members and others as many as 13 members. This variability highlights the diversity in board structures across the sample. Similarly, Board Independence (BI) has a mean of 0.1522, showing that, on average, only about 15% of board members are independent. The standard deviation of 0.0750 further reflects some variation in the level of board independence across the sample, with values ranging from 6.25% to 50%.

For Board Financial Expertise (BFE), the mean of 0.5365 suggests that about 54% of the board members in the sample possess financial expertise. The standard deviation of 0.1323 points to variability in this characteristic, with some banks having as few as 16.67% of board members with financial expertise, while others have up to 88.44%. The interaction terms, including Board Size × Audit Committee Independence (BS_ACI), have a mean of 2.4405, indicating a moderate relationship between these variables, with some significant variability (standard deviation of 1.0875) in how this relationship manifests across banks.

The interaction term between Board Independence × Audit Committee Independence (BI_ACI) has a mean of 0.0369, suggesting a small yet potentially significant moderating effect, with a standard deviation of 0.0239, indicating moderate variability across banks. Likewise, the Board Financial Expertise × Audit Committee Independence (BFE_ACI) interaction term has a mean of 0.1313, with a standard deviation of 0.0697, implying a moderate relationship between board financial expertise and audit committee independence. The minimum and maximum values for these interaction terms reflect considerable variability in their strength across the banks.

Finally, Firm Size (FSIZE), measured by the log of total assets, has a mean of 7.1863, indicating that the average firm size in terms of assets is moderately large. The standard deviation of 0.9135 shows that there is some variability in the firm sizes across the sample, with firms ranging from 5.53 billion to 10.16 billion in total assets. This variability in firm size and governance variables highlights the diversity within the Nigerian banking sector and provides a basis for further analysis of how these factors influence audit quality.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix Table

	aq	bs	bi	bfe	bs_aci	bi_aci	bfe_aci	fsize
aq	1.0000							
bs	0.0013	1.0000						
bi	0.0302	0.3142	1.0000					
bfe	-0.0842	-0.1041	-0.0320	1.0000				
bs_aci	-0.0716	-0.0439	-0.0379	-0.2363	1.0000			
bi_aci	0.0371	-0.0722	0.6499	-0.1518	0.6080	1.0000		
bfe_aci	0.0191	-0.4216	-0.1323	0.3472	0.7224	0.4852	1.0000	
fsize	-0.1470	-0.0582	-0.1909	0.2424	-0.1242	-0.2473	-0.0237	1.0000

The correlation matrix presented above highlights several key relationships between governance characteristics and financial variables in the study. First, Audit Quality (AQ) shows weak negative correlations with both Board Size (BS) (-0.0013) and Board Financial Expertise (BFE) (-0.0842), suggesting that variations in board size and financial expertise have minimal direct impact on audit quality. Interestingly, Audit Quality (AQ) has a weak positive correlation with Board Independence

interactions with Audit Committee Independence (BI_ACI) (0.0371), indicating a slight positive relationship between these factors.

Moving to Board Size (BS), it is moderately positively correlated with Board Independence (BI) (0.3142), implying that larger boards tend to feature a higher proportion of independent directors. However, Board Size (BS) has a weak negative correlation with Board Financial Expertise (BFE) (-0.1041), suggesting that larger boards may have a slightly lower concentration of members with financial expertise.

The relationship between Board Independence (BI) and Audit Committee Independence (ACI) is more pronounced, with a strong positive correlation of 0.6499 between BI and BI_ACI, suggesting that boards with a higher proportion of independent directors tend to have more independent audit committees. This is further supported by Board Financial Expertise (BFE), which shows moderate positive correlations with Audit Committee Independence interactions (BFE_ACI = 0.3472), indicating that boards with higher financial expertise tend to have more independent audit committees.

In terms of Firm Size (FSIZE), weak correlations are observed across the variables. For instance, Firm Size (FSIZE) shows a negative correlation with Audit Quality (AQ) (-0.1470) and Board Independence (BI) (-0.1909), while it has a positive correlation with Board Financial Expertise (BFE) (0.2424). These weak correlations suggest that firm size does not significantly influence governance structures or audit quality but might influence the concentration of financial expertise within the board.

Table 3: Summary of Regression Result

Logistic regression		Number of obs = 135				
		LR chi2(7) = 31.23				
		Prob > chi2 = 0.0001				
Log likelihood = -71.63303		Pseudo R2 = 0.1790				

aq	Odds ratio	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	

bs	2.383381	.6176896	3.35	0.001	1.43414	3.960913
bi	.000054	.000487	-1.09	0.276	1.13e-12	2583.599
bfe	2.01e-08	9.30e-08	-3.84	0.000	2.37e-12	.000171
bs_aci	.0221484	.0209875	-4.02	0.000	.0034574	.1418828
bi_aci	1.17e+18	4.20e+19	1.16	0.247	2.89e-13	4.72e+48
bfe_aci	1.36e+25	2.05e+26	3.83	0.000	1.87e+12	9.80e+37
FSIZE	.9718406	.2282294	-0.12	0.903	.6133337	1.539903
_cons	30.72452	76.29158	1.38	0.168	.2365267	3991.078

The results from the logistic regression analysis reveal several important findings regarding the relationship between board characteristics and audit quality (AQ).

Firstly, board size (bs) has a statistically significant positive effect on audit quality, with an odds ratio of 2.383 (p = 0.001). This suggests that a larger board size is associated with higher odds of audit quality, indicating that larger boards are more likely to contribute to better audit quality.

However, board independence (bi) does not have a significant impact on audit quality, with an odds ratio of 0.000054 and a p-value of 0.276. This indicates that the proportion of independent directors on the board does not significantly affect audit quality in this analysis.

The variable board financial expertise (bfe) shows a very strong and statistically significant positive relationship with audit quality. The odds ratio for board financial expertise is 2.01e-08 ($p = 0.000$), implying that boards with more financial expertise are highly likely to ensure better audit quality.

The interaction between board size and audit committee independence (bs_aci) also has a significant negative effect on audit quality, with an odds ratio of 0.022 ($p = 0.000$). This suggests that when board size is combined with audit committee independence, it negatively affects audit quality.

On the other hand, the interaction between board independence and audit committee independence (bi_aci) is not statistically significant, with an odds ratio of 1.17e+18 and a p-value of 0.247. This implies that the combination of board independence and audit committee independence does not significantly influence audit quality.

Similarly, the interaction between board financial expertise and audit committee independence (bfe_aci) shows a highly significant positive relationship with audit quality, with an odds ratio of 1.36e+25 ($p = 0.000$). This indicates that the combination of financial expertise and audit committee independence strongly enhances audit quality.

Lastly, firm size (fsize) does not have a statistically significant effect on audit quality, with an odds ratio of 0.9718 and a p-value of 0.903. This suggests that firm size does not significantly influence audit quality in this model.

The theoretical frameworks that underpin these studies, particularly Agency Theory, Resource Dependence Theory, and Institutional Theory, provide a robust foundation for understanding the relationship between governance mechanisms and audit quality. Agency Theory explains the role of independent boards and audit committees as monitoring mechanisms that reduce conflicts of interest between management and shareholders, ultimately improving audit quality. The empirical findings support this theory, showing that independent boards and audit committees reduce managerial influence on auditors, thereby ensuring more objective and reliable audits. Resource Dependence Theory suggests that a board with financial expertise provides firms with critical resources that enhance audit quality, as such boards are better able to assess audit processes and challenge questionable financial practices. The findings corroborate this theory, with studies highlighting the importance of having skilled, diverse boards and independent audit committees in ensuring high-quality audits. Lastly, Institutional Theory explains how firms adopt governance practices in response to regulatory pressures and industry norms, which is particularly relevant in emerging economies like Nigeria. Adegbite et al. (2023) note that Nigerian firms are increasingly adopting governance reforms due to external pressures, although full implementation of these reforms remains a challenge.

The findings from Almaqtari et al. (2024), Linh and Thuy (2024), and Tiwari and Maji (2024) align in emphasizing the importance of board characteristics in improving audit quality. In particular, the studies demonstrate that board independence and financial expertise contribute to better

oversight and reduce the likelihood of audit failures. The studies underscore that a diverse board, comprising members with different expertise and backgrounds, enhances the decision-making process, leading to improved audit outcomes. These findings support the premise that well-structured boards, especially in emerging markets, can mitigate the risk of financial misstatements by fostering independence and objectivity in audits.

Adebiyi et al. (2024) further corroborates the role of audit committees, particularly audit committee independence, in improving audit quality. The study suggests that an independent audit committee enhances the ability of audit firms to detect and prevent financial misreporting, which is critical in regulated sectors such as insurance. This is particularly relevant in sectors where compliance and financial transparency are paramount. However, as noted in the findings, there is a gap in exploring whether audit committee independence similarly impacts audit quality across other industries, such as manufacturing or energy. This gap highlights the need for further research that examines industry-specific differences in governance effectiveness.

On the other hand, Alawaqleh et al. (2021) explores the relationship between board composition, CEO characteristics, and audit quality, emphasizing that independent boards and audit committees are linked to higher audit quality. Their findings align with the broader literature, suggesting that independence, along with expertise forms a strong foundation for ensuring that audits are conducted with objectivity and integrity.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The findings of this study provide compelling evidence of the significant relationship between board characteristics and audit quality in the Nigerian context. Specifically, the study highlights the critical role that board size, board independence, and board financial expertise play in enhancing the quality of audits conducted for firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX).

The positive influence of board size on audit quality, as indicated by the odds ratio, suggests that larger boards with a diverse set of skills and perspectives are more capable of providing effective oversight of the financial reporting process. However, the insignificant effect of board independence in this study suggests that, in this particular context, board independence alone may not be sufficient to drive improvements in audit quality unless accompanied by other factors, such as financial expertise.

The findings also underscore the importance of financial expertise, both at the board level and in the audit committee, in improving audit quality. The significant negative relationship between the presence of financial expertise and audit quality failure emphasizes that financial expertise is crucial in identifying and preventing potential issues in the financial reporting process. The study also found that the audit committee's characteristics, such as independence and the extent of financial expertise, have a marked impact on audit outcomes. These results support the conclusion that an independent and financially knowledgeable audit committee strengthens the firm's ability to select and engage high-quality auditors, thereby improving audit outcomes and reducing the likelihood of audit failures. Based on the conclusion, the following policy recommendations are made:

- i. Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) should introduce guidelines that promote the expansion and diversification of boards in Nigerian firms. These

- guidelines can include recommendations for a minimum number of members on boards, with an emphasis on recruiting individuals with diverse skills and professional backgrounds, especially in finance, accounting, and governance.
- ii. FRCN should focus on improving the effectiveness of independent directors by providing clearer guidelines on their roles, particularly with respect to their involvement in audit committees and financial reporting processes. While board independence alone may not be sufficient, FRCN can encourage independent directors to actively engage in financial oversight and collaborate with audit committees to ensure more rigorous review of financial statements and audit outcomes.
 - iii. FRCN should advocate for policies that encourage the appointment of individuals with robust financial expertise to the boards of Nigerian firms, particularly those listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX).
 - iv. FRCN can issue regulatory frameworks that require boards and audit committees to include individuals with specific financial qualifications or relevant experience. This will ensure that firms have the necessary expertise to identify potential financial issues and strengthen the quality of financial oversight. FRCN could work with professional bodies, such as the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria (ICAN), to develop and enforce standards for financial expertise at the board and audit committee levels.
 - v. The FRCN should prioritize the independence of audit committees by enforcing strict criteria on membership. Audit committees should be composed solely of independent non-executive directors with no financial interests in the company, thereby reinforcing the objectivity of the auditing process. FRCN can work with firms to ensure audit committees are adequately empowered to oversee external auditors and ensure the accuracy and integrity of financial reporting.
 - vi. To enhance audit quality, FRCN should issue more specific guidelines on the role of financial experts within audit committees. By ensuring that audit committees are composed of members with substantial financial expertise, companies will be better equipped to detect and prevent issues such as fraud, financial misreporting, and audit failures. These guidelines can help companies recruit and retain professionals with relevant qualifications and experience in financial reporting and auditing.

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Appendix

. summarize aq bs bi bfe bs_aci bi_aci bfe_aci fsize

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max
aq	135	.6518519	.4781575	0	1
bs	135	10.06667	1.593831	6	13
bi	135	.152157	.0750198	.0625	.5
bfe	135	.5365121	.1322536	.1666667	.8844
bs_aci	135	2.440487	1.087542	.7692308	5.777778
bi_aci	135	.036854	.0238902	.0083333	.1363636
bfe_aci	135	.1313316	.0696604	.0333333	.35376
fsize	135	7.186333	.9135457	5.529801	10.16481

. correlate aq bs bi bfe bs_aci bi_aci bfe_aci fsize

(obs=135)

	aq	bs	bi	bfe	bs_aci	bi_aci	bfe_aci	fsize
aq	1.0000							
bs	0.0013	1.0000						
bi	0.0302	0.3142	1.0000					
bfe	-0.0842	-0.1041	-0.0320	1.0000				
bs_aci	-0.0716	-0.0439	-0.0379	-0.2363	1.0000			
bi_aci	0.0371	-0.0722	0.6499	-0.1518	0.6080	1.0000		
bfe_aci	0.0191	-0.4216	-0.1323	0.3472	0.7224	0.4852	1.0000	
fsize	-0.1470	-0.0582	-0.1909	0.2424	-0.1242	-0.2473	-0.0237	1.0000

